

REPERCUSSION OF CORONA ON THE STAKEHOLDERS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

D. P. Derain Smily

Assistant Professor,

Shri Krishnaswamy College for Women

Abstract:

In this paper on Repercussion of Corona on the stakeholders of higher educational institutions, the effect of COVID on the stakeholders of HEIs is discussed elaborately. This period where transition is taking place in every sector, the HEIs have seem to be much affected due to this crisis. Namely the stakeholders of the Institutions like students, teachers, parents, Community members and Alumnae are influenced. This COVID has hindered the process of delivering quality content on the part of Educators as well as receiving the quality of content as it is by the Students. Though technological advancements in Education have been helping the stakeholders to a larger extent to sustain, there are lot more derailment happening in the history of education system in terms of giving access towards basic infrastructural facilities like uninterrupted power supply, faster internet connectivity, employability to all households and thereby increasing the standard of living. This new normal is being expected to exist, henceforth there should be major reforms in the educational sector so as to deliver quality content to the students, thereby contributing to the national objectives. The need of strategic planning is emphasised, where an intellectual committee has to be appointed to look into the matter and formulate strategies considering virtual classrooms. A revolution in online education is much awaited, so as to strengthen educational sector which is a pillar of the nation.

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Introduction:

The higher educational institution's main focus is on giving quality education to the students. The governments lauded efforts and institutions individual efforts for maintaining reputation, expanded education into the society, thereby ensuring that every student out of their Junior College entered into higher educational institution. Thus education in our country was in accordance to the fulfilment of the national goals. Because of the unexpected situation which came across the globe in the year 2020, things were not the same and started to travel in the opposite direction. Though the educational institutions strived higher in sustaining their quality the resultant seemed to be less than expectations. Every stake holders of higher educational institutions namely the students, teachers and parents went through the difficult phase in the history of education. Although we say that higher education institutions concentrate on quality assurance, sustenance and improvement, it was very difficult to achieve it practically by reinforcing rules and regulations as per the requirements of new era. The institutions continuously strived harder to deliver quality, but the output was not equivalent to the input efforts taken by those institutions. It would need another strategic planning for educational sector to fall in line with the previous trend.

Objectives Of The Study

- To analyse the impact of specific technologies in the field of education.
- To study the effect of the COVID on higher educational institutions.
- To know the strong influence of COVID upon the stakeholders of higher educational institutions.

Research Methodology

In this paper, descriptive research design is used to give an in depth view on impact of covid on stakeholders of higher educational institutions. It includes descriptive facts and qualitative information. In this study, data is given based on real life experience, personal observation and testimonies of people associated with educational institutions.

Impact Of Specific Technologies In The Field Of Education

Technology has a great impact on education. We are living in a decade where technological advancements are common. The recent advancements in the field of education enlarged the classroom boundaries, gave wider scope of content, paved way for fun learning, gave access to open forums, poured information at a tap for 24/7 etc. The advent of technology in education is advantageous as well as carries equal disadvantages.

Effect of technology on students

It is widely known fact that in last two years there has been great increase in number of students owning smartphone. Though it is said that technology is used for collaborating and fun learning, the sad part is students are seen over using smartphones which has led to inattentiveness, depression, smartphone addict, emotional instability etc. During online sessions, the students using various applications in smartphones log in and listen to lectures. In these online sessions, their listening tendency is limited to few minutes after which they look into other work or use other applications in background.

With the advent of artificial intelligence in smartphones where Apple's Siri, Amazon's Alexa, Google Assistant play a greater role in the life of students. Students are much addicted to these virtual assistants and tend to be more lazy than normal. In spite of effective classes, fact filled lectures, assignments, seminars, projects, case studies, question and answer sessions etc, the incapability in students is visibly seen. This can be lack of direct control of teachers over the students. The added reason is online examinations, where the students find this open book concept of online examinations much easier than the offline examinations held in universities. The personal connect with each individual is easy in classrooms than virtual classrooms. Even though we say self-study is effective medium of knowledge gaining, the students have lost their competitive spirit because of lack of interpersonal relationship and face to face communication.

Effect of technology on Teachers

It is obvious that teachers are new to the transforming educational system where many new reforms have taken place. Few teachers are technically driven whereas others are new to it. Though few teachers are technically upgraded, this new educational transformation has led to frustration, stress and many other ill health conditions. It is seriously difficult for the teachers to track and attend each and every student's progress. Only best students are given best attention whereas others are left unfocused. The students sitting at home and attending their online sessions face major threats from their family itself. The environment in which they are acts a major influencer and this is beyond their control. Unlike classrooms, where the only focus is on studies, at home, their level of concentration seems to be lower and out of control. As India being developing nation, battling improper power supply, improper Internet connectivity the students cannot be questioned easily. This is also a major threat for the teachers where the students have readymade

answers to support their inefficiency and incapability. The teachers are also afraid of third party listening to the session where they can be questioned easily in case of any silly mistakes made by them.

Like in physical classrooms, where the sessions could easily be extended, in virtual classrooms it is impossible to make the students listen to continuous sessions. The teachers has to find out various means of fun learning applications to keep their students engaged. This increases the pressure on the teachers to constantly upgrade them. Also the teachers are restricted to usage of free version of certain applications in which enrolment of students are limited.

Effect of technology on Parents

Parents are new to the steps technically upgraded environment. Many higher education institutions have shifted to online payment. Though it has paved the way for digital India, the parents find it difficult to make online payments. They also have a second thought that why should high amount to be paid for online sessions. Few illiterate parents, blindly believe their children. Children's also easily mislead their parents by just having a smart phone and headset saying that they are attending online class. It is also difficult for parents having two or more children, to check in to their additional responsibility of buying a smartphone or other gadgets for online sessions.

Thus technology has primarily impacted educational sector.

Effect Of The Covid On Higher Educational Institutions

Taking into consideration of the current pandemic situation, the UGC has permitted the state government to take their own decisions for their students. The various state governments across the nation appointed a committee to check into the higher education status. The committee recommended to reduce the syllabus so as to ease the student's burden. Though the syllabus have been reduced, students find excuses and cut their online classes. This cannot be questioned by the educational institutions. The current framework drawn by the government has not fallen in line with the national development. In spite of equipping the teachers with the latest technological developments, it is difficult for the teachers to mentor their students in a proper way. Parents default fee payments. Excess use of smartphones of students have created lack of quality education as they always put them busy with their smartphones. It is also difficult for the institutions to track for examinations and other day to day activities of the students. As the institutions have started to concentrate on online fun learning, the students take everything for granted and fun. Academics is not seriously focused.

Influence of Covid upon The Stakeholders Of Higher Educational Institutions

The stakeholders of higher educational institutions are students, teachers, parents, community and alumnae. The effect of covid is seen affecting all the stakeholders. With respect to students, they find it difficult to cope with recent technical advancements in the field of education because of various factors like poor standard of living, improper power supply, poor Internet connectivity etc. Placements in higher education institutions have decreased as most of the organisations are self-reliant with their employees. The unemployment status has gone up in the nation. With respect to teachers, though they are equipped with latest technical knowledge, they feel to be pressurized from all sides. There is also fear among teachers about insecurity in job because of this online education. The content delivery is not as strong as in physical classrooms. With respect to parents, they find it difficult to cope up with digital India which has become a part and parcel of life in this new era. They tend to trust their children and fulfil their needs. The students do not utilize the opportunity is given rather focus only on their smartphone applications. With respect to community, the educational institutions have stopped community outreach programs, which focused only on developing the community people. on the part of Alumnae, their contribution towards higher education institutions have reduced because of this pandemic.

Conclusion

Technological advancements in Education have been helping in unearthing of valuable insights and the ability to develop and adapt on an ongoing basis. If recent technical advancements are applied widely, lakhs of students will be able to benefit from it. At the same time there would also be lakhs of students who will not be able to benefit out of this recent developments as they are not even provided with basic infrastructural facilities. The effect of Covid on the stakeholders of higher educational institutions are quite many. They have influenced in positive as well as negative way by imparting knowledge as well as imparting not to do things to the society. To maintain the quality in higher educational institution strategic planning is most required, where an intellectual committee has to be appointed to look into the matter and formulate strategies considering virtual classrooms. There has to be major reforms in the educational sector so as to make learning effective and efficient without burdening the teachers, students and parents. A revolution in online education is much awaited, so as to strengthen educational sector which is a pillar of the nation.

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